

Webpage Views as a Proxy for Angler Pressure and Effort: Insights from Bayesian Networks

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1 Abstract

1 Reliable angler activity data inform fisheries management. Traditionally, such data are gathered through
2 surveys, but an innovative cost-effective approach involves utilizing online platforms and smartphone
3 applications. These citizen-sourced data were reported to correlate with conventional survey information.
4 However, the nature of this correlation—whether direct or mediated by intermediate variables—remains
5 unclear. We applied Bayesian networks to data from conventional surveys, the Angler's Atlas website,
6 the MyCatch smartphone application, and environmental data across Alberta and Ontario, Canada, to
7 detect probabilistic dependencies. Using Bayesian model averaging, we quantified the strength of connec-
8 tions between variables. Waterbody webpage views were directly related to daily and weekly-aggregated
9 boat counts in Ontario (51% and 100% probability) and to weekly-aggregated creel survey-reported
10 fishing duration in Alberta (100%). This highlights the value of citizen-sourced data in providing unique
11 insights beyond meteorological factors, with online interest serving as a potentially reliable proxy for
12 angler pressure and effort.

13

14 **Keywords:** Angler activity, Bayesian network, citizen-sourced data, citizen-reported data, conventional
15 surveys, machine learning

16 2 Introduction

17 Recreational fishing is a popular activity across the globe, with more than 10% of people participating
18 and catching billions of fish every year, contributing economic and social benefits (Arlinghaus and
19 Cooke, 2009; Kelleher et al., 2012; Hyder et al., 2018). Many recreational fisheries are facing overfishing,
20 mortality, and fish diseases (Post et al., 2002; Cooke and Cowx, 2004; Lewin et al., 2006). Comprehensive
21 assessment data on resources (e.g., fish population and species) and on fishery (e.g., effort and selectivity)
22 may enable recreational fisheries management to prevent crises through measures like size and bag
23 regulations (Post et al., 2008; Venturelli et al., 2017).

24 Data can be collected through conventional surveys such as creel surveys and aerial surveys (Eero
25 et al., 2015). Creel surveys are conducted by direct interactions with anglers, either on-site while they
26 are fishing or at the conclusion of their fishing trips (Murphy et al., 1996). The collected data is limited
27 in time and space as the collection can be expensive and time-consuming (van Poorten et al., 2015;
28 Vølstad et al., 2006). Nevertheless, these conventional surveys are often considered the most reliable
29 sources of data on angler activity, providing information that is generally assumed to represent reality.

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30 Consequently, cost-effective citizen-sourced data became popular (Fischer et al., 2023; Gutowsky
31 et al., 2013). Mobile applications (apps) are modern sources of citizen-reported data. A survey on
32 experts in the recreational fishery field showed that in most countries, angler app data usage is likely to
33 increase significantly over the next 5–10 years (Skov et al., 2021). Websites also serve as an additional
34 tool for gathering data on angler activity (Martin et al., 2012). Anglers utilize these platforms to seek
35 real-time updates on fishing conditions and to share information about their fishing expeditions (Sims
36 and Danylchuk, 2017).

37 Nevertheless, citizen-sourced data do not readily represent that of conventional surveys. Angler apps
38 used for collecting fishing data may be subject to biases due to non-random participation. Who uses
39 these apps can be influenced by factors such as smartphone ownership and demographics (Venturelli
40 et al., 2017). This could result in data skewed towards certain groups (Jiorle et al., 2017). There may
41 even be intentional data manipulation, because some anglers wish to influence regulations (Sullivan,
42 2003). The design of the app, location of users, and internet connectivity can also bias the data
43 (Papenfuss et al., 2015; Jiorle et al., 2017).

44 Despite these limitations, several studies demonstrated the potential of citizen-sourced data to serve
45 as a supplementary or alternative source for conventional survey data, particularly with respect to catch
46 rates and angler pressure (i.e., the intensity of fishing activity, often measured by total fishing effort,
47 number of anglers, or hours fished; Table 1) (Jivthesh et al., 2022; Johnston et al., 2022; Papenfuss et al.,
48 2015). For example, the iNaturalist website and app provided comprehensive data with a high level of
49 completeness compared to other reporting methods such as telephone, email, and mixed-mode approaches
50 (Taylor et al., 2022). Data from iAngler app and creel surveys conducted by the Marine Recreational
51 Information Program (MRIP) showed minimal differences, with discrepancies exhibiting an almost zero
52 central tendency (Jiorle et al., 2016). Likewise, mean catch rates reported via Fangstjournalen app
53 platform were similar to those obtained through conventional surveys on a Danish island (Gundelund
54 et al., 2021).

55 However, the nature of the dependence between citizen-sourced and conventional surveys remains
56 unclear. Specifically, if the relationship is indirect and mediated by some intermediate variables, then
57 the use of citizen-sourced data to predict conventional survey outcomes would be limited, if not zero.
58 For example, if citizen-reported catch rates are indirectly related to creel-based catch rates through the
59 intermediate variable temperature (e.g., cold weather discourages angling and reporting), knowing the
60 temperature alone would suffice to predict creel-based catch rates—citizen-reported catch rates provide
61 no further information.

62 This defined our research goal: Is there a direct or indirect relationship between citizen-sourced
63 and conventional survey-based angler activity measured by catch rates, fishing duration, number of
64 trips, and number of boats? To answer this question, we employed Bayesian networks (BNs) (Koller
65 and Friedman, 2009), a type of probabilistic graphical model that allows the detection of dependencies
66 between variables. Our case study was the Lower Bow River and Upper Oldman River within three
67 fisheries management zones in Alberta, Canada, in 2018, as well as 98 randomly selected lakes across
68 15 management zones in Ontario, Canada, in 2018 and 2019. The target species included brook trout,
69 walleye, and lake trout. Webpage views from the Angler’s Atlas website and fishing trips and catches
70 reported by anglers through the Angler’s Atlas website and MyCatch app in Alberta and Ontario were
71 used as citizen-sourced data. Conventional survey-reported datasets included creel surveys in Alberta
72 and aerial surveys in Ontario. The environmental variables for both provinces included air temperature,
73 total precipitation, wind speed, relative humidity, solar radiation, and degree days for the waterbodies.

74 3 Materials and Methods

75 First, we discretized the data collected from the mentioned variables in Alberta and Ontario. Second,
76 we learned a BN for each dataset using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) score (Figure 1)
77 and analyzed the direct and indirect relationships between the variables within the BNs. Finally, we
78 employed Bayesian model averaging (BMA) to quantify the uncertainty associated with the estimated

Table 1: Examples of previous research on comparing citizen-sourced data to conventional surveys on angler activity.

App or Online Platform	Input	Conventional Survey	Studied Variables	Time Span	Methods	Location	Conclusion
Fangstjournalen (Gundelund et al., 2021)	date, location, effort, target species, number caught and retained or released	roving creel survey, aerial survey, recall survey	mean catch rate, number of anglers	2019	bootstrapping, comparative analysis, regression	Danish island of Funen	Citizen science data had the potential to supplement traditional surveys or act as an alternative source of catch and effort data.
iNaturalist (Taylor et al., 2022)	tag number, taxonomic ID, disposition of fish	telephone, email, mixed survey	report completeness, capture location precision	2019	Kruskal-Wallis test	Oklahoma	There was a significant difference in three reporting modes.
MyCatch (Johnston et al., 2022)	catch rate, fishing effort, and angler registration information	mail, creel, gillnet survey	spatial distribution, fishing landscape, catch estimates	2018-2019	zero-inflated negative binomial regression, linear regression	Alberta	General trends between the app data and conventional data were similar.
iAngler (Jiorle et al., 2016)	angler registration information, fishery-specific data, waterbody information	NOAA's MRIP survey	mean catch rate	2012-2013	negative binomial distribution	Florida	There was a high degree of similarity between the angler app and creel survey datasets' catch/trip estimates.
iAngler (Papenfuss et al., 2015)	angler registration information, fishery-specific data, waterbody information	creel survey	lake popularity	2010-2014	linear relationship	Alberta	There was a linear relationship between the frequency of visits reported by the iAngler app and the number of angler visits estimated by creel surveys.

Table 2: Summary of raw (original), daily-aggregated, and weekly-aggregated survey-based/citizen-sourced/combined datasets, highlighting the mean of non-zero values and the count of zeros for conventional survey-based and citizen-sourced variables.

Data	Number of samples	Variable	Mean of non-zero values	Number of zeros
Alberta Creel survey-based (raw data)	3714	Creel fishing duration (hour)	4.06	171
		Creel number of trips (trips per day)	40.04	0
		Creel number of fish caught	2.33	1787
Alberta Citizen-sourced (raw data)	1986	App fishing duration (hour)	0.54	1753
		App number of trips (trips per day)	1.15	1753
		App number of fish caught	0.42	60
		Webpage views	2.47	0
Alberta (daily-aggregated and combined-final)	185	Creel fishing duration (hour)	3.25	4
		Creel catch rate (catch per hour)	0.77	10
		App fishing duration	5.95	110
		App catch rate	0.63	132
		App number of trips	1.47	110
		Webpage views	16.80	26
Alberta (weekly-aggregated and combined-final)	66	Creel fishing duration (hour)	64.41	1
		Creel catch rate (catch per hour)	0.79	3
		App fishing duration	52.79	28
		App catch rate	0.98	29
		App number of trips	14.26	28
		Webpage views	58.77	23
Ontario Aerial survey-based (raw data)	3118	Number of boats	4	1532
Ontario Citizen-sourced (raw data)	8621	App fishing duration (hour)	5.58	0
		App number of trips (trips per day)	1.11	0
		App number of fish caught	7.33	2532
		Webpage views	1.81	0
Ontario (daily-aggregated and combined-final)	1128	Number of boats	7.99	654
		App fishing duration (hour)	6.78	1110
		App catch rate	1.74	1105
		App number of trips	1.06	1110
		Webpage views	1.68	850
Ontario (weekly-aggregated and combined-final)	320	Number of boats	55	38
		App fishing duration (hour)	18	0
		App catch rate	1.64	58
		App number of trips	2.94	0
		Webpage views	5.28	59

Figure 1: A conceptual illustration of the methodology used in this paper, that is the process of collecting data through conventional surveys, smartphone applications, and online platforms, followed by the construction of a Bayesian network to aid fishery management in decision-making. An angler utilizes online platforms to find information about waterbodies and report fishing experiences and uses a smartphone app to record fishing trip data. Creel surveys or aerial surveys gather information about the angler trips. The data is then used to construct the Bayesian network structure to reveal the conditional dependencies between the conventional survey and citizen-sourced variables in the presence of meteorological variables as potential confounders. Fishery managers may leverage the insights derived from this network structure to implement relevant actions, such as stocking and regulations. The management decision-making did not take place in this project and was not part of the methodology.

79 connections between the variables.

80 3.1 Data

81 The Alberta case study comprised the lower section of the Bow River and the upper section of the
82 Oldman River and its major tributaries in southwestern Alberta, from June to October 2018. The
83 Ontario case study included 98 lakes in Ontario. The data sources included the Angler’s Atlas website
84 and correspondent mobile app MyCatch, two creel surveys, an aerial survey, and a weather simulation
85 model, described below.

86 Citizen-sourced data

87 Citizen-sourced data were collected by the Angler’s Atlas website and MyCatch mobile app. The
88 Angler’s Atlas platform, established in 1999 by Goldstream Publishing Incorporated based in Prince
89 George, British Columbia, Canada, provides detailed information on 330,000 waterbodies across Canada
90 through its website (www.anglersatlas.com). Each waterbody has its own webpage featuring details
91 such as location, popular species, and markers for hotspots and boat launches. The webpages can be
92 viewed by anyone and do not require a membership on the platform. Anglers can use these webpages to
93 gather trip-planning information or to report details about their fishing experiences. Variable “webpage
94 views” was defined as the number of unique visits on a day. Several webpage views by the same individual
95 were counted as one view. “Webpage views” can be considered as an indicator of angler pressure, because
96 visiting a specific waterbody’s webpage reflects people’s interest in obtaining information about the
97 waterbody and planning trips (Xiang et al., 2015). Webpage visits in the last few days (seven in our
98 case) were considered since trips are typically planned a few days in advance (Nyblom, 2014).

99 On April 1, 2018, the MyCatch mobile app was launched by the Angler’s Atlas team and app data
100 collection began on May 11, 2018, through email campaigns targeting the subscribers of Angler’s Atlas
101 in Alberta (Johnston et al., 2022). Through both the Angler’s Atlas online platform and the MyCatch
102 app, anglers could report details about their fishing trips, such as date, location, duration, and number
103 of fish caught by species. Anglers could also report trips with no catches. The primary caught species
104 reported in Alberta and Ontario were brook trout, walleye, and lake trout. The data were anonymized
105 by daily aggregation and included only completed trips, i.e., those with fully reported information on the
106 trip. When a trip was reported for a specific waterbody, it indicated that the trip took place anywhere
107 on that waterbody. We refer to the collected data as “citizen-sourced data,” with no distinction between
108 the app and online platform.

109 We used citizen-sourced data from the entire Bow River and Oldman River systems, which span all
110 three fisheries management zones in Alberta. There were 233 reports of fishing trips from these two
111 river systems between May 11 and October 31, 2018. For Ontario, a total of 8,621 fishing trips were
112 reported over 1,670 unique waterbodies and 310 unique days between May 19, 2018 and August 29,
113 2019 (Figure 2).

114 For each waterbody and day i , the data included the total number of trips, denoted N_i , and for each
115 trip j the number of fish caught C_{ij} and the time spent fishing D_{ij} . We computed the total fishing
116 duration D_i^{total} [hour], total number of fish caught C_i^{total} [number of fish], and mean catch rate $CPUE_i$
117 (“catch per unit effort”) [fish/hour], for each day i , as follows:

$$(1) \quad D_i^{total} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} D_{ij},$$

$$(2) \quad C_i^{total} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} C_{ij},$$

$$(3) \quad CPUE_i = \frac{C_i^{total}}{D_i^{total}}.$$

121 For simplicity, we refer to app-reported D_i^{total} as “app fishing duration” and $CPUE_i$ as “app catch
 122 rate.” These formed the two app variables used in this study. The other citizen-sourced variable was
 123 “webpage views” presenting the number of times a waterbody’s webpages was visited in the last seven days.

124 125 **Creel surveys**

126 Data from two creel surveys in Alberta in 2018 were used (Johnston et al., 2022). The first survey
 127 was conducted by Alberta Environment and Parks (AEP) along the approximately 100 kilometers of
 128 Lower Bow River, from June through the end of November 2018 (Christensen et al., 2020). The second
 129 creel survey was carried out by the Alberta Conservation Association (ACA) along a stretch of 199
 130 kilometers encompassing the Upper Oldman River and its principal tributaries, the Livingstone River,
 131 Dutch Creek, and Racehorse Creek, from June to October 2018 (Hurkett and Fitzsimmons, 2019). We
 132 used creel data on both rivers which were collected from angler interviews during roving surveys at the
 133 public access points (Hurkett and Fitzsimmons, 2019; Ripley and Council, 2006; Malvestuto, 1996).
 134 The surveys were conducted across spatial and temporal strata. Spatially, this contained four reaches
 135 on the Bow River and three on the Oldman River system. Temporally, this happened during shifts in
 136 the morning (8:00–15:00) or evening (15:00–22:00)—although the exact hour and date of each interview
 137 was recorded. During interviews, 2751 anglers from the Bow River (across 122 days) and 963 anglers
 138 from the Oldman River (across 88 days) were requested to provide information about their fishing trips,
 139 including the date, time duration of the trip, and quantity of fish caught. Angler interviews included
 140 both complete and incomplete trip data. We excluded two samples due to daily fishing durations
 141 exceeding 24 hours.

142 We obtained the following creel-survey variables in the same way as with the corresponding app
 143 variables, using Equations 1 to 3: “total fishing duration of anglers sampled on day i ” $D_i^{total, sampled}$,
 144 “number of fish caught by anglers sampled on day i ” $C_i^{total, sampled}$, and “catch per unit effort of anglers
 145 sampled on day i ” $CPUE_i$. As creel surveys were not designed to measure total fishing duration, we
 146 instead used the mean value of the variable, denoted D_i^{mean} [hour/trip] on day i as follows:

$$(4) \quad D_i^{mean} = \frac{D_i^{total, sampled}}{N_i^{sampled}}.$$

147 where $N_i^{sampled}$ is the total number of trips reported by anglers sampled on day i . For simplicity, we
 148 refer to the creel survey-reported D_i^{mean} as “creel fishing duration” and $CPUE_i$ as “creel catch rate”,
 149 which formed the two survey variables in the Alberta dataset.

150 151 **Aerial surveys**

152 We utilized data from Ontario’s inland lake ecosystem collected through the Broad-scale Monitoring
 153 (BsM) program. The dataset included 98 randomly selected lakes over 50 ha, stratified by spatial (15
 154 fisheries management zones), temporal (weekend/holiday and weekday), and lake-size categories. Data
 155 were gathered during 101 aerial surveys conducted between 9:00 and 17:00 over 78 randomly selected
 156 days from June to August in 2018 and 2019 (BsM cycle 3). The variable “number of boats,” was defined
 157 as the number of actively fishing boats observed during the surveys, serving as an indicator of angler
 158 pressure and the only survey variable in the Ontario dataset.

159 160 **Meteorological data**

161 Daily averages of meteorological data, considered as potential intermediate variables, were obtained
 162 using the BioSIM tool (Régnière et al., 1996). BioSIM is a software developed by Natural Resources
 163 Canada that runs weather-driven simulation models using geographic weather data. Based on the four
 164 nearest weather stations within a radius of 300 km from the centroid of the waterbody, the software
 165 adjusted the data for elevation, latitude, and longitude differences, and restored variability to long-term
 166 averages. Historical daily weather observations were utilized, and a bi-linear interpolation method was
 167 applied (Régnière et al., 2017). We used the software to obtain data for the waterbodies, focusing on
 168 variables known to be related to or influencing angler’s behavior, such as the daily air temperature

169 (Gundelund et al., 2022; Kendall et al., 2021), precipitation (Shaw et al., 2021), wind speed (Gundelund
170 et al., 2022; Agmour et al., 2020), relative humidity (Shaw et al., 2021), solar radiation (Shaw et al.,
171 2021; Cooke et al., 2017; Speers and Gillis, 2012), and degree days (Speers and Gillis, 2012).

172 A temporal binary day-type variable “is weekend” was used to indicate whether the fishing trip
173 occurred on a weekday or a weekend (Kendall et al., 2021).

174

175 **The Alberta and Ontario datasets**

176 We constructed two final (daily-aggregated) datasets: the Alberta dataset and the Ontario dataset
177 (Table 2). The Alberta dataset was created by combining the creel survey data and app data for the two
178 river systems on days when creel data were available. Each sample of the dataset included six angler
179 activity variables: “app catch rate,” “app fishing duration,” “app number of trips,” “webpage views,”
180 “creel catch rate,” and “creel fishing duration,” along with the seven auxiliary variables described earlier.
181 The dataset had a total of 185 daily samples: 101 from Bow River and 84 from Oldman River, and an
182 overall of 75 reported fishing trips from citizen-sourced data. There were initially 233 reported trips in
183 Alberta. However, during the merging of the app data with the creel data, zero values were assigned to
184 app variables that did not have a value at the specified date and waterbody in the creel dataset. These
185 zero assignments to citizen-sourced variables were not data imputation. The reason why there was no
186 data for a certain waterbody or day was that no one reported on that day and for that waterbody. Thus,
187 by definition, the corresponding app variables would be zero. In the same way, the Ontario dataset was
188 formed by combining aerial survey data with app data for the waterbodies and dates with available
189 aerial data, resulting in 1,128 daily samples over 98 waterbodies and 18 citizen-sourced reported trips.
190 Each sample included five angler activity variables: “app catch rate,” “app fishing duration,” “app
191 number of trips,” “webpage views,” and “number of boats,” and the same seven auxiliary variables used
192 in the Alberta data (Table 3; Supplementary Material Figures S1, S2, and S3).

193

194 **Discretization**

195 Continuous variables were discretized because the applied package for the BN learning algorithm
196 required discrete data. Non-binary variables were discretized into three bins using the equal quantile
197 method, ensuring that each bin contained approximately an equal number of samples (Sun and Shenoy,
198 2007) (Supplementary Material, Figures S4, S5, and S6). Consequently, each variable had the statuses
199 “low,” “medium,” and “high” (Figures S4, S5, and S6). Discretization into three bins was shown to be
200 optimal in previous applications of BNs in ecological systems (Milns et al., 2010; Yu et al., 2004). The
201 discretization was performed separately for the Alberta and Ontario datasets.

202 If the majority of the values of a variable were zero, the first bin included only the zero values, and
203 the remaining values were discretized into two bins with an equal number of samples. In the Alberta
204 dataset, this was the case with the variables “app number of trips” (59%), “app fishing duration” (59%
205 zeros), and “app catch rate” (71% zeros). In the Ontario dataset, this applied to the variables “number
206 of boats” (58% zeros), “app catch rate” (99% zeros), “app number of trips” (98% zeros), “app fishing
207 duration” (98% zeros), “webpage views” (75% zeros), and “total precipitation” (57% zeros).

208 Due to the high proportion of zero values in the datasets, we conducted an additional experiment
209 on two weekly-aggregated datasets for waterbodies in Alberta and Ontario. Each sample was assigned
210 the calendar week number based on its calendar date. Then citizen-sourced and survey variables were
211 aggregated on a weekly basis, e.g., “number of boats” would indicate the total number of boats surveyed
212 during the calendar week. Meteorological variables were averaged over the days of the week for which any
213 of the survey-reported variables were available, and “is weekend” was removed. In Ontario, although the
214 aggregation reduced the dataset to 320 samples, it decreased the percentage of zeros in the app-reported
215 and survey variables to a maximum of 18% and 12%, respectively. For data discretization, the quantile
216 method was applied to all variables except for “total precipitation,” which had a high proportion of
217 zeros (43%). For this variable, the first bin was designated to represent zero values, while the nonzero
218 values were divided into two additional bins (bins 2 and 3) using the quantile method. In Alberta, the
219 aggregated data included 66 weekly samples, with a maximum of 44% zeros in app variables and 35% in

Table 3: List of variables included the Alberta and Ontario datasets.

Variable	Description	Alberta dataset	Ontario dataset
App catch rate (fish/hour)	Mean citizen-reported number of fish caught per hour	✓	✓
App number of trips	Total citizen-reported number of trips per day	✓	✓
App fishing duration (hour)	Total citizen reported fishing hours per day	✓	✓
Webpage views	Number of views of the waterbody webpage over the last 7 days	✓	✓
Creel catch rate (fish/hour)	Mean number of fish caught per hour recorded in the creel data	✓	×
Creel fishing duration (hour/trip)	Mean fishing hours per trip per day recorded in the creel data	✓	×
Number of boats	Number of boats per day recorded in the aerial survey	×	✓
Air temperature (°C)	Mean daily air temperature of the waterbody	✓	✓
Total precipitation (mm)	Total daily both liquid and solid precipitations	✓	✓
Wind speed (km/hour)	Mean daily wind speed	✓	✓
Relative humidity (%)	Mean daily relative humidity	✓	✓
Solar radiation (Watt/m ²)	Mean daily amount of solar energy received per square meter	✓	✓
Degree days (°C)	Summing days with $\geq 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ from April 1st each year	✓	✓
Is weekend	Whether the date is a weekend	✓	✓

220 “webpage views.” For data discretization, the quantile method was performed for all variables, except for
 221 “app catch rate” (44% zeros values), “app fishing duration” (42% zeros), “app number of trips” (42%
 222 zeros), and “webpage views” (35% zeros). Similarly, for these variables, the first bin was allocated to
 223 represent zero values, and nonzero values were divided into two bins using the quantile method.

224 3.2 Bayesian network structure and analysis

225 While the concept of direct and indirect relatedness can be challenging to investigate, a directed acyclic
 226 graph (DAG) can be used to make definitions precise and undertake analysis (Ramazi et al., 2022). In a
 227 causal model that is represented by a DAG, the parents of each node are considered as the *direct* causes
 228 of that variable and the ancestors as the *indirect* causes. More generally and out of the framework
 229 of causality, one can define direct and indirect *relationships* without DAGs by using the notion of
 230 *probabilistic conditional independence*. Given a specified set of random variables, two variables X and
 231 Y are said to be directly related if they neither are marginally independent nor become independent
 232 conditioned on any subset of the other variables. In contrast, variables X and Y are indirectly related if
 233 they are dependent but become independent once conditioned on a subset of the other variables, which
 234 we refer to as *intermediate variables*. Variables X and Y are not (probabilistically) related if they are
 235 marginally/statistically independent (Nadkarni and Shenoy, 2001; Eden et al., 1992).

236 A BN is a tool to identify conditional independencies among specified variables. A BN consists of a
 237 *structure* that is a DAG over the variables considered as nodes and *parameters* that are the conditional
 238 probability distributions of each variable conditioned on its parents in the DAG (Koller and Friedman,
 239 2009; Ramazi and Kalantari, 2023). In the structure, an edge between two variables implies a direct
 240 relationship: a dependence that does not turn into independence regardless of what other variables are
 241 observed (conditioned on). Conditional independence in a BN is captured by the notion of *d-separation*
 242 (directed separation) in the network structure. A collider on a path is the subgraph $A \rightarrow B \leftarrow C$ on the
 243 path, that is, a triple of nodes A , B , and C where A and C are linked to B . The node B is called the

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: (a) Alberta study area, including the Lower Bow River and Upper Oldman River and its principal tributaries, where creel surveys were conducted in 2018. (b) Ontario study area, including 98 lakes where aerial surveys were conducted in 2018-2019. Region polygons were sourced from the Angler's Atlas database, while roadways and city data were obtained from www.naturalearthdata.com (10m roads and 50m populated places). The map was created in QGIS using the WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator (EPSG:3857) projection.

Figure 3: An example of a Bayesian network structure representing the direct and indirect relationships between five variables. Node X_1 is directly connected to node X_2 and indirectly connected to nodes X_4 and X_5 through node X_2 . If node X_2 is observed, X_1 becomes d-separated from variables X_4 and X_5 . This means that X_1 is independent of X_4 and X_5 given X_2 , i.e., $X_1 \perp X_4, X_5 \mid X_2$. The observed node X_2 also d-separates X_4 from X_5 . Additionally, X_1 and X_3 are d-separated if X_5 is not observed, but they become dependent if X_5 is observed.

collider node. A path between nodes X and Y is active, given observed variables Z if two conditions are met: (i) for every collider on this path, either the collider node itself or at least one of its descendants (children, grandchildren, etc.) are observed, and (ii) no other node on this path is observed. Two variables X and Y are d-separated given observed variables Z if there is no active path between X and Y in the network. Two variables X and Y being d-separated (given variable(s) Z) in a BN implies that they are independent given Z , i.e., $X \perp Y \mid Z$, where Z can be the empty set (Figure 3). Moreover, under the commonly made assumptions of faithfulness, all (conditional) independencies between the variables are also captured by the d-separations in the BN.

The BN structure readily reveals the direct and indirect relationships between the variables. The structure of the network can be obtained by searching over the space of possible DAGs and selecting the DAG with the maximum BIC (or other) score(s) indicating the simplest DAG that best fits the data (Pearl, 1988). BNs have a foundation in ecological applications (Heggerud et al., 2024; Johnson and Mengersen, 2012; Milns et al., 2010). An introduction to applying and interpreting BNs in ecological datasets is given in (Ramazi et al., 2021).

We obtained two BNs, one for the Alberta data, and one for the Ontario data using the command `learn.network` in the `bnstruc` package in R (Franzin et al., 2017), which applied the Silander-Myllymaki algorithm to find the globally optimal BN structure (Silander and Myllymaki, 2012) in terms of the BIC score. This score-based algorithm searches for the structure with the highest BIC by optimizing small BN sub-structures and then utilizing the outcomes to optimize larger structures, continuing this process until finding the optimal global BN structure. The output graphs from these algorithms are often not fully directed because there can be more than one DAG resulting in the same BIC score. This implies that flipping the direction of the undirected links in either way will yield the same BIC score, as long as it does not result in a directed cycle or a new v-structure, that is, a triple of nodes X, Y, Z , where X and Y are linked to Z and X and Y are not connected. Therefore, each of the graphs obtained by an arbitrary orientation of the undirected links can be considered as the “best” BN. Once the BN structure was obtained, we investigated the direct or indirect nature of the relationships between the angler activity variables using d-separation. The directions of the arrows may not be interpreted causally (Ramazi et al., 2021), unless further assumptions are made.

Bayesian Model Averaging

When only a single BN is used as the final model, equal trust is assigned to all links, and any uncertainty about the structure selection is disregarded (Wintle et al., 2003). Bayesian model averaging (BMA) is a solution to consider the uncertainty in the dominated network by taking the expectation of the quantity of interest across all possible network structures (Broom et al., 2012; Hoeting et al., 1999;

278 Hinne et al., 2020). For example, instead of checking whether variables X and Y are linked in the best
 279 BN structure, we find the probability of the two being linked across all possible BN structures. In the
 280 process, probabilities for the existence are given to the links, whereby links that are observed in the
 281 network structures with higher scores during the search receive higher probabilities (Liao, 2023; Hwang
 282 and Zhang, 2005; Tian et al., 2012; Madigan and Raftery, 1994). The number of possible BN structures
 283 in a global search is super-exponential (Tian et al., 2012). To reduce the computational complexity, we
 284 estimated the probability by considering only a portion of the networks (Eq. 5). Thus, a probability
 285 of 100% for a link would indicate its presence in only the sampled structures and not necessarily all
 286 structures. The sampled structures were chosen based on the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)
 287 (Brooks, 1998; Friedman and Koller, 2003) method. The MCMC algorithm involved defining a Markov
 288 Chain over the space of possible network structures, generating a set of structures through a random
 289 walk in the chain and using a scoring criterion to evaluate and probabilistically accept or reject changes
 290 to the network structure, such as adding, removing, or reversing edges (Madigan and Raftery, 1994).
 291 The expectation (probability) of two nodes X and Y being adjacent (denoted X - Y) in the “best” BN
 292 equals

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} E(X - Y) &= \sum_{\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i} P(\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i|D) f(\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i) \\ &= \sum_{\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i: X-Y \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}_i} P(\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i|D), \end{aligned}$$

293 where $\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i$ is a DAG sampled by MCMC, D is the dataset, $P(\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i|D)$ is the likelihood of the sampled DAG,

$$f(\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } X \rightarrow Y \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}_i \text{ or } X \leftarrow Y \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

294 and where the summation goes over all sampled DAGs $\hat{\mathcal{G}}_i$ (Koivisto and Sood, 2004). To obtain the
 295 probability of existing links between the variables using the MCMC algorithm, we utilized the function
 296 `plinks(bdgraph.obj)` in the `BDgraph` package version 2.72 in R (Mohammadi and Wit, 2015). The
 297 package would find the probability of undirected links only, so the probabilities that we reported were
 298 for both directions, that is the probability of a link $X \rightarrow Y$ or $Y \rightarrow X$ exists between X and Y .

299 4 Results

300 In the BN structure of the daily-aggregated Alberta dataset (Figure 4a), “creel catch rate” was directly
 301 related to “app catch rate” (edge probability 12%) and “app fishing duration,” (6%) and indirectly
 302 related to “app number of trips,” via the intermediate variables “total precipitation” and “app fishing
 303 duration.” “Creel catch rate” was also indirectly related to “webpage views,” via “app fishing duration,”
 304 “total precipitation,” and “app number of trips.” “Creel fishing duration” was indirectly related to “app
 305 fishing duration,” being d-separated given intermediate variables “solar radiation,” and “air temperature.”
 306 It was also indirectly related to “app catch rate” via the weak connection to “solar radiation” (3%). In
 307 the weekly-aggregated Alberta dataset (Figure 5a), “creel fishing duration” was directly connected to
 308 “webpage views”(100%) and d-separated from all other variables given “webpage views.” “Creel catch
 309 rate” was only connected to “solar radiation” (5%).

310 In the BN structure of the daily-aggregated Ontario dataset (Figure 4b), the aerial survey-reported
 311 “number of boats” was directly related to “webpage views” (51%). Given “webpage views,” “number of
 312 boats” was d-separated from all other variables. In the weekly-aggregated Ontario dataset, “number of
 313 boats” was directly linked to “webpage views” (100%) and “app fishing duration” (6%; Figure 5b).

(a) Daily-aggregated Alberta dataset

(b) Daily-aggregated Ontario dataset

Figure 4: Bayesian network structures from the datasets of (a) Alberta (185 daily samples) and (b) Ontario (1128 daily samples). Green nodes signify environmental and time variables, and yellow and coral nodes represent citizen-sourced and conventional survey variables, respectively. Edges indicate probabilistic dependencies between variables. The number on each is the probability of that single edge existing in the “true” network. An edge without direction can be directed in both ways as its direction has no impact on the BIC score, as long as directed cycles and new v-structures are not created.

(a) Weekly-aggregated Alberta dataset

(b) Weekly-aggregated Ontario dataset

Figure 5: The Bayesian networks constructed from the weekly-aggregated (a) Ontario and (b) Alberta datasets, with 320 and 66 weekly samples, respectively. Green nodes signify environmental and yellow and coral nodes represent citizen-sourced and survey variables, respectively. Edges indicate probabilistic dependencies between variables. The number on each edge is the probability of that single edge existing in the “true” network.

314 5 Discussion

315 We used BNs to analyze the relationship between angler activities from conventional surveys and citizen-
316 sourced data and meteorological variables in Alberta and Ontario. “Webpage views” was linked directly
317 to aerial angler pressure in daily and weekly-aggregated Ontario data and to “creel fishing duration”—an
318 indicator of angler effort—in weekly-aggregated Alberta data, suggesting that online interest may serve
319 as a strong indicator of the intensity of angler activity (i.e., pressure and/or effort). In daily-aggregated
320 Alberta, a direct but weaker connection was observed between survey-based and app-based catch rates.
321 These direct connections suggest that citizen-sourced data provide unique information on creel survey
322 variables, beyond meteorological influences.

323 To our knowledge, this is the first study to propose “webpage views” as a low-cost proxy for angler
324 activity, reflecting anglers’ tendency of checking conditions online before visiting waterbodies. However,
325 without direct evidence that webpage viewers are anglers or how they use these platforms, this remains
326 a hypothesis. The absence of a direct link between “webpage views” and creel-based variables in
327 daily-aggregated Alberta may be due to the earlier MyCatch app adoption in 2018, making anglers
328 there more reliant on the app compared to Ontario anglers in 2018–2019, who likely used the Angler’s
329 Atlas website for trip planning. Future work could explore visits to other webpages or search engine
330 trends (Martin et al., 2012) as predictors of angler pressure or effort.

331 Air temperature was connected directly to “app fishing duration” in Alberta and indirectly to
332 “number of boats” in Ontario, aligning with studies on the correlation between angler activities and air
333 temperature (Midway and Miller, 2023; Gundelund et al., 2022; Sylvia et al., 2020). Precipitation was
334 strongly connected to app-based angler pressure in both provinces—except weekly Alberta—supporting
335 the idea that changing precipitation may reduce daily trips (Hunt and Moore, 2006). Its indirect link
336 to catch rate aligns in part with evidence that precipitation shapes seasonal catch and fish dynamics
337 (Baptista et al., 2016; Guy and Willis, 1991). Daily Alberta data showed a weak creel-citizen catch
338 rate link, absent weekly, possibly contrasting prior close ties (Johnston et al., 2022; Gundelund et al.,
339 2021; Jiorle et al., 2016). Despite low-probability links, app variables might still predict daily creel rates,
340 warranting further investigation. Moreover, wind speed was linked to creel-based catch rate, consistent
341 with research indicating that wind-induced turbulence hinders boat fishing (Speers and Gillis, 2012;
342 Zischke et al., 2012; Agmour et al., 2020).

343 The high proportion of zeros in the daily datasets, especially in Ontario, reflects the inherent
344 characteristics of recreational fishing behavior and data collection methods. For app-reported variables
345 such as “app number of trips” and “app fishing duration,” zeros arise on days when no fishing activity
346 was reported on the MyCatch app, which may occur due to unfavorable weather conditions, low angler
347 participation, or non-use of the app. These zeros are not data gaps but carry meaningful information
348 about the conditions under which fishing activity or reporting does not occur. Retaining these zeros in
349 the analysis allowed us to uncover the relationships between environmental and temporal factors and
350 the absence of reporting of fishing activity, offering insights into the broader dynamics of angler activity.
351 Weekly aggregation obscured these day-to-day dynamics while highlighting broader patterns, showing
352 variables that predict weekly but not daily trends, and vice versa.

353 Analyzing a more extensive dataset from Ontario compared to Alberta, the Bayesian model averaging
354 indicated a higher probability for the detected direct relationships between the variables. Namely, in the
355 Ontario dataset, there was a great match between the results from the model averaging, which accounted
356 for multiple plausible structures, and the global search, which identified a single best-fitting structure.
357 This reinforces the credibility of the identified relationships and their relevance for understanding and
358 managing ecological systems (Lavine, 2019; Ellison, 2004). However, due to computational complexity,
359 Bayesian model averaging was performed on a sampled subset of BN structures.

360 Differences in the connections between the Alberta and Ontario datasets could result from, in
361 addition to the difference in the data sizes, ecological and social factors and differences in how the
362 variables were defined (e.g., mean or total fishing durations). Firstly, the structure of a BN depends
363 on the probabilistic dependencies between variables, which can change with the presence or absence of

364 certain variables (Kitson and Constantinou, 2024). For example, “wind speed” and “degree days” were
365 indirectly connected through intermediate variable “creel catch rate” in the Alberta dataset, but the
366 two variables were directly connected in the Ontario dataset where “creel catch rate” was absent. The
367 differences could also stem from unobserved intermediate variables. Environmental factors such as water
368 temperature and air pressure, socioeconomic factors such as angler income, and social events occurring
369 in the waterbodies can shape angler activity (Meyer et al., 2023; Dabrowksa et al., 2017; Cantrell et al.,
370 2004).

371 Secondly, differences in survey methods could introduce bias. Creel surveys recorded fishing durations
372 of incomplete fishing trips, likely leading to underestimation (Eckelbecker, 2019). Conversely, app-
373 reported fishing durations corresponded to completed trips, but it is unclear if anglers reported the time
374 actively spent fishing only or the entire trip duration, possibly causing overestimation. Additionally,
375 weather variables were averaged for entire river systems or sections, but weather conditions can vary
376 significantly at individual waterbodies, which may influence angler activities (Dippold et al., 2020).

377 Thirdly, spatial variability within and between datasets can influence angler activities and, conse-
378 quently, the BN structures. For example, the Bow River is dominated by brown trout, while the Oldman
379 River is home to cutthroat trout (Johnston et al., 2022). Anglers may be drawn to specific fish species
380 and genus, affecting catch rates and pressure (Hunt et al., 2019, 2002). Other spatial factors, such
381 as water quality, aesthetics, privacy, and accessibility impact angler choices (Hunt, 2005; Moeller and
382 Engelken, 1972; Hunt and Moore, 2006). Local income levels, fishing skills, and motivation of anglers
383 further influence behavior, but these factors are often difficult to measure (Gundelund and Skov, 2021;
384 Hunt et al., 2019).

385 This study has several limitations. First, it focuses on only two provinces. Evaluating the methodology
386 in other regions or with broader datasets would likely improve its generalizability. Second, more detailed
387 spatial, temporal, and demographic data (e.g., waterbody size, water temperature, population, and
388 income) could further clarify the relationships between conventional surveys and citizen-sourced data.
389 Third, the high proportion of zeros in the citizen-sourced dataset—particularly in Ontario—suggests
390 low app participation, probably due to limited promotion following its launch. Because the app
391 was introduced earlier and more extensively in Alberta, this discrepancy is understandable. A higher
392 percentage of reporting anglers may uncover relationships to conventionally surveyed variables. Increasing
393 engagement and accurate data collection will require user-friendly interfaces, interactive features, well-
394 designed prompts, and training for anglers Venturelli et al. (2017).

395 **Dataset availability**

396 The data underlying this article were provided by Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources under licence /
397 by permission. The data are available in Taheri Tayebi (2024).

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405 **Competing Interests Statement**

406 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

407 References

- 408 Agmour, I., Bentounsi, M., Baba, N., El Foutayeni, Y., Achtaich, N., and Aouiti, C. (2020). Impact of
409 wind speed on fishing effort. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00736-7>.
- 410 Arlinghaus, R. and Cooke, S. J. (2009). Recreational fisheries: socioeconomic importance, conservation
411 issues and management challenges. *Recreational hunting, conservation and rural livelihoods: science
412 and practice*, pages 39–58.
- 413 Baptista, V., Campos, C. J., and Leitão, F. (2016). The influence of environmental factors and fishing
414 pressure on catch rates of *diplodus vulgaris*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-015-9990-y>.
- 415 Brooks, S. (1998). Markov chain monte carlo method and its application. [https://doi.org/10.1111/
416 1467-9884.00117](https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9884.00117).
- 417 Broom, B. M., Do, K.-A., and Subramanian, D. (2012). Model averaging strategies for structure learning
418 in bayesian networks with limited data. *BMC bioinformatics*, 13:1–18.
- 419 Cantrell, R. N., Garcia, M., Leung, P., and Ziemann, D. (2004). Recreational anglers’ willingness to pay
420 for increased catch rates of pacific threadfin (*polydactylus sexfilis*) in hawaii. [https://doi.org/10.
421 1016/j.fishres.2004.01.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2004.01.003).
- 422 Christensen, P., SULLIVAN, M., and PATTERSON, B. (2020). Survey to estimate angler effort on the
423 bow river. *open.alberta.ca*.
- 424 Cooke, S. J. and Cowx, I. G. (2004). The role of recreational fishing in global fish crises. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2004\)054\[0857:TRORFI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0857:TRORFI]2.0.CO;2).
- 426 Cooke, S. J., Lennox, R. J., Bower, S. D., Horodysky, A. Z., Treml, M. K., Stoddard, E., Donaldson,
427 L. A., and Danylchuk, A. J. (2017). Fishing in the dark: the science and management of recreational
428 fisheries at night. <https://doi.org/10.5343/bms.2015.1103>.
- 429 Dabrowksa, K., Hunt, L. M., and Haider, W. (2017). Understanding how angler characteristics and
430 context influence angler preferences for fishing sites. [https://doi.org/10.1080/02755947.2017.
431 1383325](https://doi.org/10.1080/02755947.2017.1383325).
- 432 Dippold, D. A., Adams, G. D., and Ludsin, S. A. (2020). Spatial patterning of walleye recreational
433 harvest in lake erie: role of demographic and environmental factors. [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.
434 fishres.2020.105676](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2020.105676)Getrightsandcontent.
- 435 Eckelbecker, R. W. (2019). Comparing angler effort and catch rate estimates across creel survey methods
436 at three alabama reservoirs. Master’s thesis, Auburn University.
- 437 Eden, C., Ackermann, F., and Cropper, S. (1992). The analysis of cause maps. [https://doi.org/10.
438 1111/j.1467-6486.1992.tb00667.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.1992.tb00667.x).
- 439 Eero, M., Strehlow, H. V., Adams, C. M., and Vinther, M. (2015). Does recreational catch impact the
440 tac for commercial fisheries? <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsu121>.
- 441 Ellison, A. M. (2004). Bayesian inference in ecology. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.
442 00603.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00603.x).
- 443 Fischer, S. M., Ramazi, P., Simmons, S., Poesch, M. S., and Lewis, M. A. (2023). Boosting propag-
444 ule transport models with individual-specific data from mobile apps. [https://doi.org/10.1111/
445 1365-2664.14356](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14356).
- 446 Franzin, A., Sambo, F., and Di Camillo, B. (2017). bnstruct: an r package for bayesian network structure
447 learning in the presence of missing data. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw807>.

- 448 Friedman, N. and Koller, D. (2003). Being bayesian about network structure. a bayesian approach to
449 structure discovery in bayesian networks. *Machine learning*, 50:95–125.
- 450 Gundelund, C., Arlinghaus, R., Birdsong, M., Flávio, H., and Skov, C. (2022). Investigating angler
451 satisfaction: The relevance of catch, motives and contextual conditions. [https://doi.org/10.1016/
452 j.fishres.2022.106294](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2022.106294).
- 453 Gundelund, C. and Skov, C. (2021). Changes in angler demography and angling patterns during the
454 covid-19 lockdown in spring 2020 measured through a citizen science platform. [https://doi.org/10.
455 1016/j.marpol.2021.104602](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104602).
- 456 Gundelund, C., Venturelli, P., Hartill, B. W., Hyder, K., Olesen, H. J., and Skov, C. (2021). Evaluation
457 of a citizen science platform for collecting fisheries data from coastal sea trout anglers. [https:
458 //doi.org/10.1139/cjfas-2020-0364](https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfas-2020-0364).
- 459 Gutowsky, L. F., Gobin, J., Burnett, N. J., Chapman, J. M., Stoot, L. J., and Bliss, S. (2013).
460 Smartphones and digital tablets: emerging tools for fisheries professionals. [https://doi.org/10.
461 1080/03632415.2013.838133](https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2013.838133).
- 462 Guy, C. S. and Willis, D. W. (1991). Seasonal variation in catch rate and body condition for four fish
463 species in a south dakota natural lake. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02705060.1991.9665305>.
- 464 Heggerud, C. M., Xu, J., Wang, H., Lewis, M. A., Zurawell, R. W., Loewen, C. J., Vinebrooke, R. D.,
465 and Ramazi, P. (2024). Predicting imminent cyanobacterial blooms in lakes using incomplete timely
466 data. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023WR035540>.
- 467 Hinne, M., Gronau, Q. F., van den Bergh, D., and Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2020). A conceptual introduction
468 to bayesian model averaging. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245919898657>.
- 469 Hoeting, J. A., Madigan, D., Raftery, A. E., and Volinsky, C. T. (1999). Bayesian model averaging:
470 a tutorial (with comments by m. clyde, david draper and ei george, and a rejoinder by the authors.
471 <https://doi.org/10.1214/ss/1009212519>.
- 472 Hunt, L., Haider, W., and Armstrong, K. (2002). Understanding the fish harvesting decisions by anglers.
473 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10871200290089355>.
- 474 Hunt, L. and Moore, J. (2006). The potential impacts of climate change on recreational fishing in
475 northern ontario. *CABI Databases*.
- 476 Hunt, L. M. (2005). Recreational fishing site choice models: insights and future opportunities. [https:
477 //doi.org/10.1080/10871200591003409](https://doi.org/10.1080/10871200591003409).
- 478 Hunt, L. M., Camp, E., van Poorten, B., and Arlinghaus, R. (2019). Catch and non-catch-related
479 determinants of where anglers fish: a review of three decades of site choice research in recreational
480 fisheries. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2019.1583166>.
- 481 Hurkett, B. and Fitzsimmons, K. (2019). Angler survey in the upper oldman river watershed, 2018.
482 *Data Report, produced by the Alberta Conservation Association, Sherwood Park, Alta., Canada*.
- 483 Hwang, K.-B. and Zhang, B.-T. (2005). Bayesian model averaging of bayesian network classifiers
484 over multiple node-orders: application to sparse datasets. [https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCB.2005.
485 850162](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCB.2005.850162).
- 486 Hyder, K., Weltersbach, M. S., Armstrong, M., Ferter, K., Townhill, B., Ahvonen, A., Arlinghaus,
487 R., Baikov, A., Bellanger, M., Birzaks, J., et al. (2018). Recreational sea fishing in europe in a
488 global context—participation rates, fishing effort, expenditure, and implications for monitoring and
489 assessment. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12251>.

- 490 Jiorle, R., Ahrens, R., and Allen, M. (2017). Determining the utility of electronic, self-reported
491 recreational data for fisheries stock assessment. In *147th Annual Meeting of the American Fisheries*
492 *Society*. AFS.
- 493 Jiorle, R. P., Ahrens, R. N., and Allen, M. S. (2016). Assessing the utility of a smartphone app for
494 recreational fishery catch data. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2016.1249709>.
- 495 Jivthesh, M., Gaushik, M., Shibu, N., Raj, D., and Rao, S. N. (2022). A comprehensive survey of web
496 and mobile apps for fishermen. *Data, Engineering and Applications*, pages 199–211.
- 497 Johnson, S. and Mengersen, K. (2012). Integrated bayesian network framework for modeling complex
498 ecological issues. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.274>.
- 499 Johnston, F. D., Simmons, S., Poorten, B. v., and Venturelli, P. (2022). Comparative analyses with
500 conventional surveys reveal the potential for an angler app to contribute to recreational fisheries
501 monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfas-2021-0026>.
- 502 Kelleher, K., Westlund, L., Hoshino, E., Mills, D., Willmann, R., de Graaf, G., and Brummett, R.
503 (2012). *Hidden harvest: The global contribution of capture fisheries*. Worldbank; WorldFish.
- 504 Kendall, M. S., Williams, B. L., Winship, A. J., Carson, M., Grissom, K., Rowell, T. J., Stanley, J.,
505 and Roberson, K. W. (2021). Winds, waves, warm waters, weekdays, and which ways boats are
506 counted influence predicted visitor use at an offshore fishing destination. [https://doi.org/10.1016/
507 j.fishres.2021.105879](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2021.105879).
- 508 Kitson, N. K. and Constantinou, A. C. (2024). The impact of variable ordering on bayesian network
509 structure learning. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10618-024-01044-9>.
- 510 Koivisto, M. and Sood, K. (2004). Exact bayesian structure discovery in bayesian networks. *The Journal*
511 *of Machine Learning Research*, 5:549–573.
- 512 Koller, D. and Friedman, N. (2009). *Probabilistic graphical models: principles and techniques*. MIT
513 press.
- 514 Lavine, M. (2019). Frequentist, bayes, or other? <https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2018.1459317>.
- 515 Lewin, W.-C., Arlinghaus, R., and Mehner, T. (2006). Documented and potential biological impacts
516 of recreational fishing: insights for management and conservation. [https://doi.org/10.1080/
517 10641260600886455](https://doi.org/10.1080/10641260600886455).
- 518 Liao, Z. (2023). Improved bayesian network structure learning in the model averaging paradigm. *UW*.
- 519 Madigan, D. and Raftery, A. E. (1994). Model selection and accounting for model uncertainty in
520 graphical models using occam’s window. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1994.10476894>.
- 521 Malvestuto, S. P. (1996). Sampling the recreational creel. *Fisheries techniques, 2nd edition*. *American*
522 *Fisheries Society, Bethesda, Maryland*, pages 591–623.
- 523 Martin, D. R., Pracheil, B. M., DeBoer, J. A., Wilde, G. R., and Pope, K. L. (2012). Using the internet
524 to understand angler behavior in the information age. [https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2012.
525 722875](https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2012.722875).
- 526 Meyer, K. A., McCormick, J. L., Kozfkay, J. R., and Dillon, J. C. (2023). Effects of elevated water
527 temperature on cutthroat trout angler catch rates and catch-and-release mortality in idaho streams.
528 <https://doi.org/10.1111/fme.12605>.
- 529 Midway, S. R. and Miller, P. W. (2023). Heat, hurricanes, and health: Effects of natural disturbances
530 on angling effort. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0291126>.

- 531 Milns, I., Beale, C. M., and Smith, V. A. (2010). Revealing ecological networks using bayesian network
532 inference algorithms. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-0731.1>.
- 533 Moeller, G. H. and Engelken, J. H. (1972). What fishermen look for in a fishing experience. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3799256>.
- 535 Mohammadi, R. and Wit, E. C. (2015). Bdgraph: An r package for bayesian structure learning in
536 graphical models. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v089.i03>.
- 537 Murphy, B. R., Willis, D. W., et al. (1996). *Fisheries techniques*. Citeseer.
- 538 Nadkarni, S. and Shenoy, P. P. (2001). A bayesian network approach to making inferences in causal
539 maps. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217\(99\)00368-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217(99)00368-9).
- 540 Nyblom, Å. (2014). Making plans or “just thinking about the trip”? understanding people’s travel
541 planning in practice. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2014.01.003>.
- 542 Papenfuss, J. T., Phelps, N., Fulton, D., and Venturelli, P. A. (2015). Smartphones reveal angler
543 behavior: a case study of a popular mobile fishing application in alberta, canada. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03632415.2015.1049693>.
- 545 Pearl, J. (1988). *Probabilistic reasoning in intelligent systems: networks of plausible inference*. Morgan
546 kaufmann.
- 547 Post, J., Persson, L., Parkinson, E. v., and Kooten, T. v. (2008). Angler numerical response across
548 landscapes and the collapse of freshwater fisheries. <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-0465.1>.
- 549 Post, J. R., Sullivan, M., Cox, S., Lester, N. P., Walters, C. J., Parkinson, E. A., Paul, A. J.,
550 Jackson, L., and Shuter, B. J. (2002). Canada’s recreational fisheries: the invisible collapse? [https://doi.org/10.1577/1548-8446\(2002\)027%3C0006:CRF%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1577/1548-8446(2002)027%3C0006:CRF%3E2.0.CO;2).
- 552 Ramazi, P., Fischer, S. M., Alexander, J., James, C. T., Paul, A. J., Greiner, R., and Lewis, M. A.
553 (2022). *Myxobolus cerebralis* establishment and spread: a graphical synthesis. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfas-2020-0352>.
- 555 Ramazi, P. and Kalantari, H. (2023). Bayesian and Causal Bayesian Networks. <https://openlibrary-repo.ecampusontario.ca/jspui/handle/123456789/1790>. Accessed: 2024-12-26.
- 557 Ramazi, P., Kunegel-Lion, M., Greiner, R., and Lewis, M. A. (2021). Exploiting the full potential of
558 bayesian networks in predictive ecology. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13509>.
- 559 Régnière, J., Logan, J. A., Shore, T., and MacLean, D. (1996). Landscape-wide projection of temperature-
560 driven processes for seasonal pest management decision support: a generalized approach. *Decision
561 Support Systems for Forest Pest Management, Proceedings. Entomological Society of Canada, FRDA
562 Report*, 260:43–55.
- 563 Régnière, J., Saint-Amant, R., Béchar, A., and Moutaoufik, A. (2017). Biosim 11—manuel d’utilisation.
564 *Quebec, QC, Canada: Natural Resources Canada, Canadian Forest Services, Laurentian Forestry
565 Center*.
- 566 Ripley, T. and Council, T. (2006). Bow river sport fish angler survey, 2006. data report. Technical
567 report, D-2007-003, produced by the Alberta Conservation Association, Lethbridge
- 568 Shaw, S. L., Renik, K. M., and Sass, G. G. (2021). Angler and environmental influences on walleye
569 sander vitreus and muskellunge esox masquinongy angler catch in escanaba lake, wisconsin 2003–2015.
570 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257882>.

- 571 Silander, T. and Myllymaki, P. (2012). A simple approach for finding the globally optimal bayesian
572 network structure. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1206.6875>.
- 573 Sims, B. and Danylchuk, A. J. (2017). Characterizing information on best practice guidelines for
574 catch-and-release in websites of angling-based non-government organizations in the united states.
575 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2016.09.019>.
- 576 Skov, C., Hyder, K., Gundelund, C., Ahvonen, A., Baudrier, J., Borch, T., DeCarvalho, S., Erzini, K.,
577 Ferter, K., Grati, F., et al. (2021). Expert opinion on using angler smartphone apps to inform marine
578 fisheries management: status, prospects, and needs. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa243>.
- 579 Speers, J. and Gillis, D. (2012). Catch and effort variation in the commercial gillnet fishery of lake
580 winnipeg, canada, in relation to environmental factors. [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2011.](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2011.05.006)
581 05.006.
- 582 Sullivan, M. G. (2003). Exaggeration of walleye catches by alberta anglers. [https://doi.org/10.1577/
583 1548-8675\(2003\)023%3C0573:E0WCBA%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1577/1548-8675(2003)023%3C0573:E0WCBA%3E2.0.CO;2).
- 584 Sun, L. and Shenoy, P. P. (2007). Using bayesian networks for bankruptcy prediction: Some method-
585 ological issues. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2006.04.019>.
- 586 Sylvia, A., Maahs, B., and Weber, M. J. (2020). Influence of largemouth bass behaviors, angler behaviors,
587 and environmental conditions on fishing tournament capture success. [https://doi.org/10.1002/
588 tafs.10216](https://doi.org/10.1002/tafs.10216).
- 589 Taheri Tayebi, A. (2024). Webpage views as a proxy for angler pressure and effort: Insights from
590 bayesian networks [data set], <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10881645>. Accessed: 2024-12-10.
- 591 Taylor, A. T., Peeper, A. M., Chapagain, B., Joshi, O., and Long, J. M. (2022). Modern reporting methods
592 for angler tag-return studies: Trends in data quality, choice of method, and future considerations.
593 <https://doi.org/10.1002/nafm.10738>.
- 594 Tian, J., He, R., and Ram, L. (2012). Bayesian model averaging using the k-best bayesian network
595 structures. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1203.3520>.
- 596 van Poorten, B. T., Carruthers, T. R., Ward, H. G., and Varkey, D. A. (2015). Imputing recreational
597 angling effort from time-lapse cameras using an hierarchical bayesian model. [https://doi.org/10.
598 1016/j.fishres.2015.07.032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2015.07.032).
- 599 Venturelli, P. A., Hyder, K., and Skov, C. (2017). Angler apps as a source of recreational fisheries data:
600 opportunities, challenges and proposed standards. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12189>.
- 601 Vølstad, J. H., Pollock, K. H., and Richkus, W. A. (2006). Comparing and combining effort and catch
602 estimates from aerial-access designs as applied to a large-scale angler survey in the delaware river.
603 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1577/M04-146.1>.
- 604 Wintle, B. A., McCarthy, M. A., Volinsky, C. T., and Kavanagh, R. P. (2003). The use of bayesian
605 model averaging to better represent uncertainty in ecological models. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.
606 1523-1739.2003.00614.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2003.00614.x).
- 607 Xiang, Z., Wang, D., O'Leary, J. T., and Fesenmaier, D. R. (2015). Adapting to the internet: trends in
608 travelers' use of the web for trip planning. *Journal of travel research*, 54(4):511–527.
- 609 Yu, J., Smith, V. A., Wang, P. P., Hartemink, A. J., and Jarvis, E. D. (2004). Advances to bayesian
610 network inference for generating causal networks from observational biological data. [https://doi.
611 org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bth448](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bth448).
- 612 Zischke, M. T., Griffiths, S. P., and Tibbetts, I. R. (2012). Catch and effort from a specialised recreational
613 pelagic sport fishery off eastern australia. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2012.04.011>.